

CHARACTERIZATION OF UNKNOWN LINEAR SYSTEMS
BASED ON MEASURED CW AMPLITUDE

M. T. Ma and J. W. Adams
Electromagnetic Fields Division
National Institute of Standards and Technology
325 Broadway
Boulder, CO 80303
U. S. A.

Abstract

An approximate squared-magnitude function is derived from a given measured cw amplitude response to characterize an unknown linear system. Various possible system transfer functions (both amplitude and phase) and the corresponding impulse responses are then deduced. These transfer functions may or may not be minimum phase. The first impulse maximum and accumulated energy content are the greatest when the transfer function is at minimum phase.

Introduction

The total response, in time and frequency, of a linear but complex system required for assessing the system's vulnerability to an unfriendly EM environment is difficult to obtain, because the system transfer function may be unknown. In general, the response of such a system can be determined only by sophisticated time-domain (TD) measurements or by derivations from the frequency-domain (FD) amplitude and phase measurements. Unfortunately, such TD measurements or FD phase measurements require expensive equipment and special attention to radiation hazards, regulatory compliance, and even environment pollution when a testing at desirable levels is made. On the other hand, measuring amplitude response of an unknown, complex, linear system to cw excitations at low levels, indoors or outdoors, is relatively straightforward, less costly, and free from compliance and pollution concerns. Furthermore, if such measured cw magnitude can be processed to deduce an approximate system transfer function (or functions), the complete characteristics including phases and impulse responses of such a system to a general excitation are then derivable.

In this paper, we present a method to deduce the total response of an unknown linear system from a measured cw magnitude only. This is accomplished by approximating the square of the magnitude curve by a sum of rational functions (ratios of two polynomials of even orders with real coefficients), each representing a second-order transfer function for a passive network. The exact number in the sum is determined by the number of resonant frequencies displayed in the measured data. The approximation is best for matching each resonant frequency, its half-power frequencies, and the magnitude at that particular resonant frequency. Once this approximation is done, the remaining tasks of deducing system transfer functions, their amplitudes and phases, and the corresponding impulse responses are exact. Only one of the transfer functions so obtained is at minimum phase. The first maximum and accumulated energy of the impulse response is the greatest when the transfer function is at minimum phase. This first maximum is the most serious one when considered from the EMI point of view. A specific example based on the actual measurement for a linear complex system is given to illustrate the theory and computational procedures involved.

The Approach

With the knowledge developed in modern passive network theory [1, 2], we can deduce a rational transfer function $H(s)$ directly and exactly from a given squared-magnitude function $|H(j\omega)|^2$ expressed as a ratio of two polynomials of even order in ω , where the

order of the numerator polynomial is at least two degrees lower than that of the denominator polynomial. Thus, if an approximate squared-magnitude function $|H(j\omega)|^2$ in such a form can be obtained from the measured cw magnitude, which represents the response of an unknown, complex, linear system to some excitation, the task of deducing a rational transfer function and the associated phase function and impulse response is then straightforward. In this process, we essentially have assumed that the original unknown linear system, which may consist of distributed elements and other complexities, is to be approximated by a passive network with only time-invariant and lumped-constant elements. The approximation is the only one involved in the process. The exact order in the final $|H(j\omega)|^2$ depends on outstanding features in the given cw magnitude. The most important feature displaying a strong resonance at a particular frequency can be approximated by a simple second-order transfer function.

Second-Order Transfer Function

The simplest second-order transfer function takes the form

$$H(s) = A/(s^2 + as + b), \quad (1)$$

where the parameters A, a, and b are real and positive. In addition, we require

$$a < 2\sqrt{b}, \quad (2)$$

for a stable system with its complex poles in the left-half s-plane.

The outstanding features associated with the transfer function in (1) can be analyzed by examining its squared-magnitude function when $s = j\omega$,

$$|H(j\omega)|^2 = \frac{A^2}{\omega^4 - (2b - a^2)\omega^2 + b^2}, \quad (3)$$

where ω is the only variable.

In addition, when $b > a^2/2$, the resonant frequency occurs at

$$\omega_0^2 = (2b - a^2)/2. \quad (4)$$

The maximum value of (3) at ω_0 is

$$|H(j\omega_0)|^2 = A^2/(b^2 - \omega_0^4). \quad (5)$$

The relative minima of (3) are $|H(0)| = A/b$ when $\omega = 0$ and $|H(j\omega)| \rightarrow 0$ when $\omega \rightarrow \infty$.

The half-power points are obtained by solving $|H(j\omega)|^2 = |H(j\omega_0)|^2/2$ to yield $\omega^2 = \omega_0^2 \pm \sqrt{(b^2 - \omega_0^4)}$. If we denote the half-power frequency on the left side of the resonant frequency by ω_1 , and that on the right side by ω_2 , we have

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_2^2 &= \omega_0^2 + \sqrt{(b^2 - \omega_0^4)} & \text{and} \\ \omega_1^2 &= \omega_0^2 - \sqrt{(b^2 - \omega_0^4)}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The quality factor of the system may be defined as

$$Q = \omega_0 / (\omega_2 - \omega_1), \quad (7)$$

where $\omega_2 - \omega_1$ may be called bandwidth of the system.

From the application point of view, we can determine the parameters A, a, and b by reading $|H(j\omega_0)|^2$, ω_0 , and ω_2 (or ω_1) from the measured data,

$$\begin{aligned} A &= (\omega_2^2 - \omega_1^2) |H(j\omega_0)| / 2, \\ b^2 &= \omega_0^4 + (\omega_2^2 - \omega_1^2)^2 / 4, \quad \text{and} \\ a^2 &= 2[\sqrt{\omega_0^4 + (\omega_2 - \omega_1)^2(\omega_2 + \omega_1)^2 / 4} - \omega_0^2]. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

If indeed an unknown linear system can be approximated by the simple transfer function in (1) with its three parameters obtained in (8), the approximate squared magnitude for this simple system is then given by (3), the phase information by [note: the phase is defined by $H(j\omega) = |H(j\omega)| \exp(-\theta(\omega))$]

$$\theta(\omega) = \tan^{-1}[a\omega / (b - \omega^2)], \quad (9)$$

and the impulse response by

$$h(t) = \frac{A}{\beta} e^{-at/2} \sin \beta t, \quad t \geq 0, \quad (10)$$

where

$$\beta^2 = b - a^2/4.$$

The time response $R(t)$ of this simple system to a general excitation $e(t)$, cw or pulse, is then given by the convolution integral [3]

$$R(t) = e(t) * h(t). \quad (11)$$

The second-order transfer function may take another form,

$$H'(s) = A(s + c) / (s^2 + as + b), \quad (12)$$

where c is real.

This case can be handled in a similar manner with the exception that four parameters, A, a, b, and c, are now involved. They may be determined by ω_0 , ω_1 , ω_2 , and $|H(j\omega_0)|$ observed from the measured curve. Details on this are referred elsewhere [4].

Higher-Order or More General Case

For a more general case where the measured magnitude curve has N ($N > 1$) distinct resonant frequencies, it may be approximated by a sum of the elementary squared-magnitude function given in (3),

$$|H(j\omega)|^2 = \sum_{i=1}^N |H_i(j\omega)|^2, \quad (13)$$

with the required parameters A, a, and b for each $|H_i(j\omega)|$ to be determined as outlined above.

Numerical Example

We now give an example based on the real-world data shown in figure 1. The data represent the measured but normalized electric field (magnitude) of vertical polarization reflected from a helicopter when it is irradiated by an impulse. The curve in figure 1 shows four significant resonant frequencies at 16.50, 26.25, 41.0, and 53.375 MHz. The other resonance near 3 MHz is ignored because its magnitude is small, close to the background noise. It can be added, however, if necessary.

To simplify the numbers involved, we temporarily use hertz rather than megahertz. Restoration to MHz can be made later by a frequency transformation [5]. The four resonant radian frequencies are $\omega_{01} = 33\pi = 103.6726$, $\omega_{02} = 52.5\pi = 164.9336$, $\omega_{03} = 82\pi = 257.6106$, and $\omega_{04} = 106.75\pi = 335.3650$. Figure 1 indicates that the respective maximum magnitudes are 14.00 (22.92 dB), 52.52 (34.41 dB), 13.00 (22.28 dB), and 5.33 (14.53 dB). Their respective radian half-power frequencies are approximately 91.1062, 113.0973; 144.5132, 185.3540; 238.7610, 282.7433; and 326.7256, 341.1770.

Applying the procedures as presented, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \text{for } \omega_{01}, A_1 &= 3.1435(10^4), b_1 = 1.0980(10^4), \\ a_1 &= 21.5420, \text{ and} \end{aligned}$$

$$|H_1(j\omega)|^2 = 9.8816(10^8) / [\omega^4 - 2.1496(10^4)\omega^2 + 1.2056(10^8)]; \quad (14)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{for } \omega_{02}, A_2 &= 3.5377(10^5), b_2 = 2.8025(10^4), \\ a_2 &= 40.5358, \text{ and} \end{aligned}$$

$$|H_2(j\omega)|^2 = 12.5153(10^{10}) / [\omega^4 - 5.4406(10^4)\omega^2 + 7.8538(10^8)]; \quad (15)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{for } \omega_{03}, A_3 &= 1.4909(10^5), b_3 = 6.7347(10^4), \\ a_3 &= 44.3546, \text{ and} \end{aligned}$$

$$|H_3(j\omega)|^2 = 2.2228(10^{10}) / [\omega^4 - 1.3273(10^5)\omega^2 + 4.5356(10^9)]; \quad (16)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \text{for } \omega_{04}, A_4 &= 2.5723(10^4), b_4 = 1.1257(10^5), \\ a_4 &= 14.3871, \text{ and} \end{aligned}$$

$$|H_4(j\omega)|^2 = 6.6166(10^8) / [\omega^4 - 2.2494(10^5)\omega^2 + 1.2673(10^{10})]. \quad (17)$$

Adding (14) through (17), we have the final approximate squared-magnitude function

$$|H(j\omega)|^2 = 1.4903(10^{11})N(\omega^2)/D(\omega^2), \quad (18)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} N(\omega^2) &= \omega^{12} - 3.6694(10^5)\omega^{10} + 5.1348(10^{10})\omega^8 \\ &\quad - 3.4113(10^{15})\omega^6 + 1.0820(10^{20})\omega^4 \\ &\quad - 1.3940(10^{24})\omega^2 + 6.2996(10^{27}) \\ &= [\omega^4 - 2.1747(10^4)\omega^2 + 1.2577(10^8)] \times \\ &\quad [\omega^4 - 1.2098(10^5)\omega^2 + 3.9741(10^9)] \times \\ &\quad [\omega^4 - 2.2422(10^5)\omega^2 + 1.2615(10^{10})], \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

and $D(\omega^2)$ is the product of the four denominators in (14) through (17). Equation (18) is shown in figure 2 together with the component squared-magnitude functions in (14) through (17), after they are re-expressed in terms of megahertz. After converting figure 1 in magnitude (rather than in decibels) as shown in figure 3 and comparing it with figure 2, we see the approximation is good, especially in the important regions near the resonant frequencies.

Setting $|H(j\omega)|^2$ in (18) to $H(s)H(-s)|_s = j\omega$ according to the network theory [1, 2], we obtain

$$H(s)H(-s) = 1.4903(10^{11})N(-s^2)/D(-s^2), \quad (20)$$

where

$$N(-s^2) = N_1(+)N_2(+)N_3(+)N_1(-)N_2(-)N_3(-), \quad (21)$$

and

$$D(-s^2) = D_1(+)D_2(+)D_3(+)D_4(+)D_1(-)D_2(-)D_3(-)D_4(-), \quad (22)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned}
N_1(\pm) &= s^2 \pm 26.1252s + 1.1215(10^4), \\
N_2(\pm) &= s^2 \pm 71.4229s + 6.3040(10^4), \\
N_3(\pm) &= s^2 \pm 20.5139s + 1.1232(10^5); \\
D_i(\pm) &= s^2 \pm a_i s + b_i, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \text{ and } 4.
\end{aligned}$$

Since we require the system to be stable (no poles in the right-half s-plane), we have to assign $D_1(+), D_2(+), D_3(+), D_4(+)$ as the denominator for $H(s)$. Thus, $D_1(-), D_2(-), D_3(-), D_4(-)$ belongs to $H(-s)$. As far as the numerator for $H(s)$ is concerned we have many choices from (21). When $N_1(+), N_2(+), N_3(+)$ is assigned as the numerator of $H(s)$, $N_1(-), N_2(-), N_3(-)$ then belongs to $H(-s)$. In this case, there are no zeros in the right-half s-plane. The result is a transfer function with minimum phase. We then have

$$\begin{aligned}
H_m(s) &= \frac{3.8604(10^5)N_1(+)N_2(+)N_3(+)}{D_1(+)D_2(+)D_3(+)D_4(+)} \\
&= 3.8604(10^5) \sum_{i=1}^4 [(F_i s + G_i)/D_i(+)], \quad (23)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{where } F_1 &= 2.3245/10^4, \quad G_1 = 1.3664/10^2, \\
F_2 &= 5.3398/10^4, \quad G_2 = 0.8742, \\
F_3 &= -6.8335/10^4, \quad G_3 = 0.1055, \\
F_4 &= -8.3091/10^5, \quad G_4 = 1.7752/10^3.
\end{aligned}$$

Applying the inverse Laplace transform, we get the impulse response before restoring frequency in MHz,

$$h_m(t) = 3.8604(10^2) \sum_{i=1}^4 (f_i \cos \beta_i t + g_i \sin \beta_i t) \times e^{-\alpha_i t}, \quad t \geq 0, \quad (24)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
f_1 &= 0.2325, \quad g_1 = 0.1071, \quad \alpha_1 = 10.7710, \\
\beta_1 &= 104.2305; \quad f_2 = 0.5340, \quad g_2 = 5.1959, \\
\alpha_2 &= 20.2679, \quad \beta_2 = 166.1740; \quad f_3 = -0.6833, \\
g_3 &= 0.4665, \quad \alpha_3 = 22.1773, \quad \beta_3 = 258.5634; \\
f_4 &= -0.0831, \quad g_4 = 0.0071, \quad \alpha_4 = 7.1936, \text{ and} \\
\beta_4 &= 335.4422.
\end{aligned}$$

The normalized impulse response by dropping the factor $3.8604(10^2)$ in (24) is presented in figure 4. The corresponding normalized impulse response after converting frequency to MHz can be obtained simply by multiplying α_i and β_i by 10^6 .

The associated phase is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
\theta_m(\omega) &= \theta_1(\omega) + \theta_2(\omega) + \theta_3(\omega) + \theta_4(\omega) \\
&\quad - \theta_5(\omega) - \theta_6(\omega) - \theta_7(\omega), \quad (25)
\end{aligned}$$

where the first four component phases are due to the denominator in $H_m(s)$ and the last three are due to the numerator in $H_m(s)$. That is,

$$\begin{aligned}
\theta_1(\omega) &= \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{21.5420\omega}{1.0980(10^4) - \omega^2} \right], \\
\theta_2(\omega) &= \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{40.5358\omega}{2.8025(10^5) - \omega^2} \right], \\
\theta_3(\omega) &= \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{44.3546\omega}{6.7347(10^4) - \omega^2} \right], \\
\theta_4(\omega) &= \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{14.3871\omega}{1.1257(10^6) - \omega^2} \right], \\
\theta_5(\omega) &= \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{26.1252\omega}{1.1215(10^4) - \omega^2} \right],
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\theta_6(\omega) &= \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{71.4227\omega}{6.3040(10^4) - \omega^2} \right], \quad \text{and} \\
\theta_7(\omega) &= \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{20.5139\omega}{1.1232(10^5) - \omega^2} \right]. \quad (26)
\end{aligned}$$

Each of these phases varies from 0 to $\pi/2$ as ω changes from 0 to ∞ . The total phase $\theta_m(\omega)$ in (25) is plotted in figure 5 before restoring frequency to MHz. In order to express the phase in MHz, we multiply the numerator inside the arctangents by the factor of (10^6) and the constant term in the denominator by (10^{12}) .

Other 7 possible solutions for the transfer function with nonminimum phases are, in view of (20) and (21),

$$\begin{aligned}
H_{n1}(s) &= CN_1(+)N_2(+)N_3(-), \\
H_{n2}(s) &= CN_1(+)N_2(-)N_3(+), \\
H_{n3}(s) &= CN_1(-)N_2(+)N_3(+), \\
H_{n4}(s) &= CN_1(+)N_2(-)N_3(-), \\
H_{n5}(s) &= CN_1(-)N_2(+)N_3(-), \\
H_{n6}(s) &= CN_1(-)N_2(-)N_3(+), \quad \text{and} \\
H_{n7}(s) &= CN_1(-)N_2(-)N_3(-), \quad (27)
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$C = 3.8604(10^5)/[D_1(+)D_2(+)D_3(+)D_4(+)].$$

The corresponding phases and impulse responses for the nonminimum-phase transfer functions can be handled in the same manner as for the minimum-phase case. These nonminimum phases are also included in figure 5 for comparison. Clearly, $\theta_{ni} > \theta_m$. The normalized impulse responses for the nonminimum-phase cases before referring to frequency in MHz are presented in figure 6, which may be compared with figure 4. This comparison shows that the first maximum and initial rise time of $h_m(t)$ are higher than those of $h_{ni}(t)$. Details on these are omitted here, but can be found elsewhere [4].

Consideration of Energy Contents

To assess the ability of a system to withstand damage from an external unwanted excitation, it is often useful to compute the energy content in an impulse response. The total energy may be defined as [6]

$$E = \int_0^{\infty} h^2(t) dt, \quad (28)$$

where $h(t)$ represents the impulse response for minimum-phase or nonminimum-phase cases. The exact unit for E depends on that for $h(t)$.

In view of Parseval's theorem [7], the energy content is also equal to

$$E = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |H(j\omega)|^2 d\omega. \quad (29)$$

Since $h_m(t)$ and $h_{ni}(t)$ as derived for the example presented in the previous section originate from the same approximate squared-magnitude in (18), their respective total energies in $0 \leq t \leq \infty$ are equal even though $h_{ni}(t) < h_m(t)$ initially. If, however, we replace the upper integration limit ∞ in (28) by a finite T , we can analyze the accumulated energy absorbed by the system under consideration. The results for the example in (18) are presented in figure 7. We see that $E_{ni} \leq E_m$. They are equal only when $T \rightarrow$

∞. This implies that the system with minimum phase is the worst case as far as the potential damage to the system is concerned.

Conclusions

We have used a simple method known in network theory to determine the complete characteristics for an unknown linear system from a given cw magnitude response only. These characteristics include possible different transfer functions, their phases, and the corresponding impulse responses. Only one transfer function has minimum phase. The main achievement is to deduce an approximate squared-magnitude function in the form of a ratio of two even polynomials based on the outstanding features, such as resonant frequencies and bandwidths, contained in the given measured magnitude. The remaining procedures for obtaining the complete system characteristics are exact. We also have shown that the minimum-phase case, through its associated impulse response and accumulated energy content, constitutes the most conservative estimate for the initial threat to the system by an external unfriendly source.

References

- [1] F. M. Reza and S. Seely, Modern Network Analysis, McGraw-Hill, New York, NY, 1959.
- [2] M. E. Van Valkenburg, Network Analysis, Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs, NJ, 1959.
- [3] D. K. Cheng, Analysis of Linear Systems, Addison Wesley, Reading, MA, 1959.
- [4] M. T. Ma and J. W. Adams, "Characteristics of unknown linear systems deduced from measured cw magnitude," NIST Journal of Research, vol. 98, no. 3, May-June, 1993.
- [5] N. Balabanian, Network Synthesis, Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs, NJ, 1958.
- [6] R. A. McConnell, "An energy analysis of the EMP damped sinusoid," Proc. IEEE National Symp. on EMC, May 23-25, 1989.
- [7] A. Papoulis, The Fourier Integral and its Applications, McGraw-Hill, New York, NY, 1962.

Figure 1. A sample measured results.

Figure 2. The approximate magnitude function, together with the four component magnitude functions.

Figure 3. Same as figure 1, but expressed in number, rather than in dB.

Figure 4. Normalized impulse response of the linear system whose approximate magnitude function is shown in figure 2. This is for the minimum-phase case.

Figure 5. Phases of the sample system whose approximate magnitude function is shown in figure 2.

Figure 6b. Continuation of figure 6a.

Figure 6a. Normalized impulse response of a sample system with its approximate magnitude function given in figure 2, but with nonminimum phases.

Figure 7. Energy contents of the sample system whose approximate magnitude function is given in figure 2.